

The “OKTÁV” project for facilitating international mobility¹ Uluslararası hareketliliği kolaylaştırmaya yönelik “OKTÁV” projesi

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ABSTRACT

This study presents some categorizational possibilities for research and practices of international student mobilities and shows on Project "OkTáv", which is being implemented through the cooperation of six universities from four countries—Hungary, Romania, Serbia, and Slovakia—and aims to support university students enrolled in teacher education programs. Building on a series of prior research projects, the OkTáv Project develops and implements the following outcomes: a) A literature review addressing international responsibility; b) Documentation of good practices in international mobility; c) Attitude, opinion, and satisfaction surveys for students and lecturers, applicable as pre- and post-tests in university courses, preparing participants for international mobility; d) Methodological guidelines for these surveys; e) A book presenting the theoretical framework of the OkTáv Project; f) A 30-hour university course titled “World Citizens in Education: Fundamentals of Project Planning”; Alternative teacher training modules linked to international mobility; g) A specialized teacher training course; h) A methodological guide for the “Educational Cosmopolitans: International Perspectives in Teacher Training” train-the-trainer program. The study was supported by the Tempus Public Foundation (2024-1-HU01-KA220-HED-000248326).

ÖZ

Bu çalışma, uluslararası öğrenci hareketliliği araştırmaları ve uygulamaları için bazı sınıflandırma olanakları sunmakta ve dört ülkeden (Macaristan, Romanya, Sırbistan ve Slovakya) altı üniversitenin işbirliğiyle hayata geçirilen ve öğretmen yetiştirme programlarına kayıtlı üniversite öğrencilerini desteklemeyi amaçlayan "OkTáv" Projesi'ni ele almaktadır. Önceki bir dizi araştırma projesine dayanarak, OkTáv Projesi aşağıdaki sonuçları geliştirmekte ve uygulamaktadır: a) Uluslararası sorumluluğu ele alan bir literatür taraması; b) Uluslararası hareketlilikte iyi uygulamaların belgelenmesi; c) Üniversite derslerinde ön ve son test olarak uygulanabilen, katılımcıları uluslararası hareketliliğe hazırlayan öğrenci ve öğretim üyeleri için tutum, görüş ve memnuniyet anketleri; d) Bu anketler için metodolojik kılavuzlar; e) OkTáv Projesinin teorik çerçevesini sunan bir kitap; f) “Eğitimde Dünya Vatandaşları: Proje Planlamasının Temelleri” başlıklı 30 saatlik bir üniversite dersi; uluslararası hareketlilikle bağlantılı alternatif öğretmen eğitim modülleri; g) Uzmanlaşmış bir öğretmen eğitim kursu; h) “Eğitim Kozmopolitleri: Öğretmen Eğitiminde Uluslararası Perspektifler” eğitim yetiştirme programı için metodolojik bir kılavuz. Çalışma, Tempus Kamu Vakfı (2024-1-HU01-KA220-HED-000248326) tarafından desteklenmiştir.

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Introduction

The internationalization of education is a key factor in the development of both primary/secondary and higher education institutions, particularly through programs such as Erasmus+ and other cross-border mobility initiatives (Aye & Bocsi, 2023). The topic of international mobility has therefore become a popular area of research (Khanam & Joshi, 2025; Roshid & Ibna Seraj, 2023; Halasi & Pintér Krekity, 2025a) and has also encouraged educational and higher education institutions to support and promote international mobility through targeted programs.

This review follows this dual approach and is therefore organized into two major thematic sections. The first shorter part focuses on general research approaches to international student mobility. The second part introduces the Project "OkTáv", which is being implemented through the cooperation of four countries—Hungary, Romania, Serbia, and Slovakia—and aims to create a flexibly applicable course in teacher education, which will prepare teacher candidates to be able to use the international development opportunities of public education and vocational training as students and early career teachers. They will learn about the steps of strategy building, the available programs, applications, and funding opportunities, the tools for successful project implementation and dissemination, and expand their related (pedagogy, psychology) methodological toolkit.

Research Approaches About International Student Mobility

The following lines summarize three possible categorizations of research on international student mobility: a) the first categorization is based on whether the research is quantitative or qualitative in nature, b) the second is a topic- focused categorization, c) the third categorization is based on the OxIPO model of learning. Studies on international mobility can be grouped into three main categories based on their quantitative or qualitative characteristics:

a) Quantitative research often focuses on periodic and/or national data (for example, the number of participants in mobility programmes by their demographic, socio-economic, and academic characteristics, or on the duration of mobility, the quantitative data of sending and host countries and institutions, funding, etc.). Example: Weber & Van Mol (2023), Zimmermann et al. (2021), Kosztyán et al. (2021). For characteristics of the international mobility of Hungarian university students, see e.g., Pusztai et al., 2016; Aye & Bocsi, 2023.

b) Qualitative examination can concentrate on such psychological aspects of participants as their experiences or emotional, motivational or career plan aspects of international mobility (the central question of these last kinds of studies is: “Why does someone participate—or not participate—in international mobility?” See, for example: Vögtle, (2019), Valls-Figuera et al. (2023), Ivasciuc et al. (2025).

c) The third type of research on international mobility uses hybrid (or mixed) methods. In these cases, qualitative data obtained during data collection are also analysed quantitatively. E.g.: Janik et al. (2023). This type of categorization can help identify the kind of quantitative and/or qualitative indicators of an international student mobility program. On the other hand, it can be used during the planning of programs for international mobility. Thirdly hand, it can be useful from the aspects of planning and realizing of effectiveness studies of these programs.

According to another, topic-focused categorization, the study of international mobility may include the following, non-mutually exclusive thematic areas:

1. The examination of groups and actors involved in international mobility:

1.1. Research focusing on sending and host countries or its networks. A typical research question concerns the quantitative indicators characterizing a given country, as well as comparisons between countries. E.g.: de Fedotova (2022), Janik et al. (2023), Breznik et al. (2024), Apsite-Berina et al. (2023).

1.2. Analyses concerning sending and host institutions or their networks. These studies examine the characteristics of international mobility either from the perspective of a given institution or through comparative analyses of a selected group of institutions - see: European University Association (2025). A special case, when

the examined units are not educational or higher educational institutes, but one or more international offices for international mobility (Eriçok, 2023).

1.3. Studies focusing on individuals. In these, independent variables may include, for example, teacher/student status, age, gender, socio-economic status, discipline/field of study, nationality, etc. Dependent variables may include motivational aspects related to international mobility, indicators of planned/realized or non-planned mobility, academic/work performance outcomes, career plan, and career, etc. E.g.: Valls-Figuera et al. (2023), Eurostudent (2025 – a citation from this: “Student mobility has long been a focus topic of EUROSTUDENT. Besides information on different types of mobility experiences students have had during the course of their studies (e.g. duration, destination, funding, organisation, etc.), EUROSTUDENT also investigates reasons for not going abroad during studies by asking students about the obstacles they face. Detailed data on internships abroad are available as well.”).

2. The examination of the characteristics of international inbound and outbound mobility, for example, programs, its year or other time interval, duration, the number of participants, the mode and extent of funding, and patterns according to sending and host countries/organizations, or the impact of mobility on the individuals' learning achievements or career, etc. E.g.: Granja & Visentin (2024), Ivasciuc et al. (2025).

3. Systematic literature review of publications on international mobility of students and teachers. Examined variables specific to publications may include: title, type, year, content, country, publishers, editors, authors, and type and length of the publication, etc. E.g.: Khanam & Joshi (2025), Roshid & Ibna Seraj (2023), Halasi & Pintér Krekity (2025a).

Thematic categorization can be useful for defining units during sampling or program planning for international student mobility.

The third categorization option is based on the components of the OxIPO model of learning (Mező and Mező, 2019). According to this model, learning (including learning related to international student mobility) is an information processing process, its main components are: learning organization, input (the curriculum or information intake), process (information processing), and output (the use of information, its products). The acronym “OxIPO” is formed from the first letters of these components (note: “x” symbolizes multiplication and refers to the interaction of the learning organization and the other three components)(Mező & Mező, 2014; 2020). From the aspect of the OxIPO model, international student mobility can be analyzed according to the following research and development activities:

Learning organization: Research and/or practical efforts to organize international mobility can be classified here. Example: the work of organizing offices and their research (Ericok, 2023). Input: methodological aspects of the content and delivery of international student mobility and/or preparatory training and courses. Example: Net16. Process: research and development opportunities for the acquisition of an international student mobility curriculum and the cognitive/emotional processing of experiences. See: Zimmermann et al. (2021).

Output: research and practice into the results, consequences, effects, products of international student mobility and/or their promotion (e.g., Granja & Visentin, 2024). OxIPO model-based categorization can be useful to plan and realize research and practice of international student mobility programs from the aspect of information processing. The above lines also presented three possible categorizations of research on international student mobility, which can be a good starting point for practical measures and programs aimed at facilitating these mobilities.

On the basis of the literature (Halasi & Pintér Krekity, 2025a) and surveys among students in connection with international mobility, six European universities established the "OkTáv" project to support the students' international mobility in the teacher education programs. The following lines introduce the project, its goals and products, and the cooperating international institutions.

About the project OkTáv

The entitled project “OkTáv” is an international initiative supported by Tempus Public Foundation (Erasmus+ Project ID: 2024-1-HU01 KA220-HED-000248326 - Erasmus+ Partnerships in Higher Education) with 400,000 EUR (see: Net1). Its Hungarian full title is “Oktatási világpolgárok: nemzetközi szemlélet a tanító- és tanárképzésben” means “Educational Cosmopolitans: International Perspectives in Teacher Training” in English. The acronym “OkTáv” refers to the Hungarian title. The project leader is Dr. habil László Révész (Eszterházy Károly Catholic University, Hungary). The duration of the project is: 27 months (it runs from 01.10.2024 to 31.12.2026).

Aims and Products. The OkTáv Project develops and implements the following outcomes:

A literature review addressing international responsibility, language learning and teaching, and the exploration of digital learning opportunities. Lenke Major overviewed the literature in the Republic of Serbia and the Republic of Croatia; Györgyi Majorosné Kovács, Anita Molnár, and Krisztina Radics summarised the Hungarian characteristics. Romanian literature is reviewed by Iuliana Borbély, Edith Debrenti, Erzsébet Szász, Zsuzsanna Dégi, and Ingrid Tomonicska (Románia). Péter Tóth, Kinga Horváth, Renáta Hajabáč Machová, Attila Mészáros, Alexandra Nagyová, Katalin Sýkora Hemády, and Szilvia Szabó wrote about international mobility in the Slovak Republic. The work document is ready (Halasi & Pintér Krekity, 2025a), and the publishing is in progress.

Documentation of good practices in international mobility across Hungarian (Mező, 2025a, 2025b; Molnár, 2025a, 2025b; Orgoványi-Gajdos, 2025a, 2025b), Romanian (Borbely et al., 2025a, 2025b, 2025c; Tódor & Pál, 2025a, 2025b), Slovakian (Horváth, 2025a, 2025b), and Serbian (Borsos, 2025a, 2025b, 2025c) schools. The work document is ready (Halasi & Pintér Krekity, 2025), and the publishing is in progress.

Attitude, opinion, and satisfaction surveys for students and lecturers, applicable as pre- and post-tests in university courses preparing participants for international mobility. Attitude is a psychological term referring to the totality of knowledge, emotions, and behavioral intentions related to its subject. Within the framework of the project, on the one hand, the input and output measurement of students' attitudes towards pursuing international studies, on the other hand, the input and output data collection and processing of instructors participating in the training of trainers, and the necessary measurement tools were developed. As part of the measurement tools for the output measurements, the satisfaction of students and participants with the training of trainers courses is also measured. The questionnaires are ready, and their testing and use are in progress.

Methodological guidelines for the administration and interpretation of these surveys. The work document is ready, and the publishing is in progress.

A 30-hour university course titled “Educational Cosmopolitans: International Perspectives in Teacher Training”. A detailed description of the course can be found in the e-publication presented in the following paragraph.

An online coursebook entitled “Educational Cosmopolitans: International Perspectives in Teacher Training” that contains the curriculum and the associated university course to encourage and prepare for international mobility. The publication consists of five main chapters. The first chapter lays the foundations for international mobility. The second chapter approaches internationalization from the perspective of mobility and internationalization tools. The third chapter discusses the educational aspects of internationalization. The fourth chapter discusses areas of management related to international mobility, such as resource generation and application writing. Finally, the fifth chapter aims to provide assistance in implementing measurement, evaluation, and dissemination tasks related to international mobility. The online coursebook is free and available (see: Net14).

Institution-specific course descriptions for Hungarian, Romanian, Slovakian, and Serbian Universities, partner institutions. The course descriptions are ready, and the testing of courses is in progress in the collaborative universities of the four countries.

An online task bank of 68 tasks for the courses, encouraging international mobility (Net15). Users can search by activities or series of activities, levels (1-5), and students with or without special needs. According to the starting webpage of the task bank of the OkTáv project (Net16), "Developing pedagogical knowledge requires not only theoretical foundations but also active practice. Our interactive tasks provide opportunities for teacher trainees to test their knowledge and gain practical experience. The various types of tasks help develop problem-solving and reflective thinking skills." The task collection is ready, and the development of its websites (Net15) is in progress.

The trainers' manual edited by Pál et al. (2025) contains Hungarian (Ferenc Mező, Attila Farkas), Serbian (Lenke Major), Slovakian (Katalin Sýkora Hernády, Alexandra Nagyvová, and Szilvia Szabó), and Romanian (Enikő Pál, Erika-Mária Tódor, Zsuzsanna Dégi & Ingrid Tomonicska) authors' recommendations to the OkTáv courses. "Each chapter of this manual is structured similarly. After the general information, the methodological guide contains the following: 1) ideas for preparatory / ice-breaking activities to introduce the given unit, 2) ideas for mastering the basic concepts in the given curriculum section, 3) tips and methods for processing the theoretical knowledge of the given curriculum section, 4) reflections on the examples in the given chapter, and 5) draws attention to aspects that the instructor should definitely know about the given curriculum. After that, the tasks in the curriculum and/or other supplementary tasks are presented, with comments on the given tasks." (see: Pál et al., 2025, p 4.). The manuscript of this methodological guide for the "Educational Cosmopolitans: International Perspective in Teacher Training" train-the-trainer program (Net16) is ready, and the publishing is in progress.

A specialized teacher training course. This training prepares the instructors teaching the student course to professionally deliver the course they are developing. Its curriculum is ready. The first training was held at the Sapientia Hungarian University of Transylvania (Csíkszereda, Romania, September 2-4, 2025).

Collaborating partners. The project is implemented jointly by six Hungarian-speaking higher education institutions from four countries. The partner institutes of the project consortium are: Eszterházy Károly Catholic University (Hungary, note: the project is coordinated by this institute), Partium Christian University (Romania), Sapientia University of Transylvania (Romania), Selye János University (Slovakia), Hungarian Teacher Training Faculty of the University of Novi Sad, Subotica (Serbia), and Milton Friedman University (Hungary). In the rows below, these universities are introduced.

Eszterházy Károly Catholic University. According to the self-introduction of this institution on the official website of the Oktáv project (see: Net2), the Eszterházy Károly Catholic University (EKKE), a state-recognised medium-sized institution located in north-eastern Hungary, operates two campuses—in Eger and Jászberény—and comprises five faculties: Humanities, Economics and Social Sciences, Informatics, Pedagogy, and Natural Sciences. EKKE provides a wide range of academic opportunities, including 9 higher-education programmes, 32 bachelor's degrees, 13 master's degrees, 19 teacher-training programmes, 2 art programmes and several five-year non-university courses (see: Net3). The institution also hosts two doctoral schools, one focusing on history and the other on education. At present, the University offers two double-degree study options: a BSc in Viticulture and Wine Engineering conducted in partnership with Bordeaux Sciences Agro in France, and an MSc in Computer Science developed jointly with Johannes Kepler University in Linz, Austria.

In addition, the University delivers numerous adult-education opportunities, including language training, intensive thematic courses, specialised professional programmes and teacher-training modules.

EKKE has participated in many projects supported by national and EU funding schemes. For the organised and effective coordination of these initiatives, the University maintains a dedicated Project Department. Teacher training is a key element of EKKE's educational portfolio, while internationalisation efforts are embedded as a horizontal priority within its institutional development strategy.

Christian University of Partium. As it is readable in the self-introduction of this institute (Net4): The Christian University of Partium carries forward the centuries-old heritage of Hungarian-language higher education in Transylvania, serving as the first independent and accredited Hungarian university established in Romania after the political changes of 1989.

Grounded in its Charter, the institution is committed to shaping a modern, competitive university that reflects the Christian values and Hungarian spirit it has intentionally embraced, while drawing on the long-standing traditions of Hungarian academic life. Its mission is to provide equal educational opportunities for the Hungarian community of Transylvania and Partium and to prepare highly qualified, competitive professionals in line with the standards of quality education and academic excellence. By educating future intellectuals, the university also assumes an important cultural role, helping to maintain and further develop the heritage of the Hungarian mother-tongue culture through a continuous supply of trained experts (see: Net5).

Sapientia Hungarian University of Transylvania. Sapientia Hungarian University of Transylvania (Sapientia UTE), established in 2001, serves as a higher education institution for Romania's Hungarian community. It was created to offer academic opportunities to the Hungarian-speaking minority and to promote high-level scientific research. Sapientia UTE consists of four faculties (Faculty of Mackenzie, Faculty of Cluj-Napoca, Faculty of Târgu Mureş, Faculty of Sfântu Gheorghe), along with a Teacher Training Institute, which has been functioning across three sites for over a decade (see: Net6 and Net7).

The University's mission includes preserving universal human and Christian values, ensuring quality teaching and research, sustaining the Hungarian educational heritage in Transylvania, and operating with consistency and transparency. It is also committed to advancing professionalism and scientific excellence, building a modern and coherent institutional system that responds to regional demands, and developing extensive partnership networks founded on openness, dependability, dedication, and mutual respect.

Selye János University. As can be seen from the introductory document on the Oktáv project website (Net8): Situated within the European region, Selye János University (SJE) is dedicated to ensuring high-quality education and scientific work across its bachelor's, master's, and doctoral programmes. It also strives to promote a knowledge-based society, uphold moral values, nurture creativity and a well-balanced personality, and support free thought and scientific inquiry. By broadening access to higher education in Slovakia, the University seeks to gradually raise both the number of young Hungarians obtaining degrees and the overall educational level of the Hungarian population in Slovakia.

The mission of SJE's Faculty of Teacher Education is to offer flexible, diverse, and high-quality training in the disciplines and programmes specified and accredited in its foundational documents. Its primary goal is to prepare teachers for Hungarian-language kindergartens, primary schools, and secondary schools, fully aligned with contemporary expectations. Well-known Hungarian and international experts ensure the professional foundations of its study programmes, with the humanities complemented by a strong emphasis on natural science education.

A defining characteristic of both the University and the Faculty of Teacher Education is their commitment not only to the advancement of the immediate region but also to the preservation and growth of the Hungarian community in Slovakia. With a strong sense of social responsibility, the Faculty aims to serve as an intellectual hub for the institution's broader surroundings, the region at large, the labour market, and the national community (see: Net9).

University of Novi Sad. Based on the self-introduction of this institute (see: Net10 and Net11): affiliated with the University of Novi Sad, the Hungarian Teacher Training Faculty has been functioning since 2006 and stands as one of Serbia's key state higher education institutions with a long-standing tradition in Hungarian-language instruction. It is accredited as a scientific research centre and represents the only higher education faculty in Serbia where all programmes are taught exclusively in Hungarian.

The institution provides bachelor's and master's programmes in primary school teaching and kindergarten education, along with bachelor's programmes in communication and dormitory education. Research activities at the university mainly concentrate on these academic fields.

In addition, the Hungarian Teacher Training College holds three academic professional conferences each year, offering opportunities for international cooperation, scholarly exchange, and global visibility. The Erasmus and Makovecz Programmes, which promote both international mobility and mobility among Hungarian communities in the Carpathian Basin for students and teachers, support these aims as well.

Milton Friedman University. Milton Friedman University (MFU), together with its sponsor EMIH, aims for the renewed institution to assume a prominent position within Hungarian higher education (see: Net12 and Net13). It views itself simultaneously as a service-oriented, cooperative, and innovative university, and it works to embody all three dimensions at once. This blended profile is reinforced by offering a wide selection of bachelor's and master's programmes in areas that respond more directly to market needs. As higher education undergoes a major transformation today, a new strategic approach has become essential.

The university seeks to preserve its significant contribution to the fields of economics, communication, international studies, and political science, while also retaining its established role in adult education and implementing an effective internal restructuring. The academic portfolio of this university continues to grow, highlighted by the introduction of pilot programmes and teacher training in 2020. The long-term vision of Milton Friedman University rests on remaining an independent institution—valued by both students and employers—that continues to progress despite demographic, economic, and global challenges.

Closing thoughts

International student mobility can be examined from multiple perspectives, and studies on this topic can also be categorized according to various criteria. These categorizations are useful not only for organizing the theoretical knowledge related to the subject but can also provide a theoretical framework for designing and implementing programs that support international student mobility.

One such university program supporting the international mobility of students in teacher education is the OkTáv program, which is implemented in collaboration with six European universities. The curriculum for this program has been completed, the first courses developed within the program have been launched at the partner universities, and measurements necessary for evaluating their impact are currently underway.

Declaration of Conflicting Interests

The author declare no potential conflicts of interest with respect to the research, authorship, and/or publication of this article.

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Statements of Publication Ethics

I hereby declare that the study has not unethical issues and that research and publication ethics have been observed carefully.

Researcher Contribution Rate

The author wrote this work himself.

Ethics Committee Approval Information

I hereby declare that, within the scope of this study, I have not collected data from participants using any surveys, interviews, focus groups, observations, experiments or other interview techniques; that I have not conducted experiments on humans or animals, etc.; that I have not breached the Data Protection Act; and that, as the corresponding author, I have informed the other authors regarding the completion of this document; As the corresponding author, I declare that this study falls under the category of research not requiring ethical committee approval.

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GENİŞLETİLMİŞ ÖZET

Eğitimin uluslararasılaşması, özellikle Erasmus+ gibi programlar ve diğer sınır ötesi hareketlilik girişimleri aracılığıyla hem ilk/orta öğretim hem de yükseköğretim kurumlarının gelişiminde kilit bir faktördür (Aye & Bocs, 2023). Bu derleme bu ikili yaklaşımı benimsemekte olup, bu nedenle iki ana tematik bölüme ayrılmıştır. İlk ve daha kısa bölüm, uluslararası öğrenci hareketliliğine yönelik genel araştırma yaklaşımlarına odaklanmaktadır. İkinci bölümde ise Macaristan, Romanya, Sırbistan ve Slovakya olmak üzere dört ülkenin işbirliğiyle yürütülen ve öğretmen adaylarını, hem öğrenci hem de kariyerinin başındaki öğretmenler olarak kamu eğitimi ve mesleki eğitimin sunduğu uluslararası gelişim fırsatlarından yararlanabilecek şekilde hazırlayacak, öğretmen eğitiminde esnek bir şekilde uygulanabilir bir ders oluşturmayı amaçlayan “OkTáv” Projesi tanıtılmaktadır. Aşağıdaki satırlar, uluslararası öğrenci hareketliliği üzerine yapılan araştırmaların üç olası sınıflandırmasını özetlemektedir: a) ilk sınıflandırma, araştırmanın nitel mi yoksa nicel mi olduğuna dayanmaktadır, b) ikincisi konuya odaklı bir sınıflandırmadır, c) üçüncü sınıflandırma ise OxIPO öğrenme modeline dayanmaktadır. Uluslararası hareketlilik üzerine yapılan çalışmalar, nicel veya nitel özelliklerine göre üç ana kategoriye ayrılabilir: a) Nicel araştırmalar genellikle dönemsel ve/veya ulusal verilere odaklanır (örneğin, hareketlilik programlarına katılanların demografik, sosyoekonomik ve akademik özelliklerine göre sayıları, hareketliliğin süresi, gönderen ve ev sahibi ülkeler ile kurumların nicel verileri, finansman vb.). b) Nitel inceleme, katılımcıların deneyimleri veya uluslararası hareketliliğin duygusal, motivasyonel ya da kariyer planı yönleri gibi psikolojik yönlerine odaklanabilir (bu son tür çalışmaların temel sorusu şudur: “Bir kişi neden uluslararası hareketliliğe katılır ya da katılmamaktadır?”) c) Uluslararası hareketlilik üzerine yapılan üçüncü tür araştırmalar, hibrit (veya karma) yöntemler kullanır. Bu durumlarda, veri toplama sırasında elde edilen nitel veriler de nicel olarak analiz edilir. Örneğin: Janik ve ark. (2023). “OkTáv” adlı proje, Tempus Kamu Vakfı tarafından 400.000 avro tutarında desteklenen uluslararası bir girişimdir (Erasmus+ Proje Kimliği: 2024-1-HU01 KA220-HED-000248326 - Erasmus+ Yükseköğretim Ortaklıkları) (bkz.: Net1). Projenin Macarca tam adı “Oktatási világpolgárak: nemzetközi szemlélet a tanító- és tanárképzésben” olup, İngilizceye “Eğitimde Kozmopolitler: Öğretmen Eğitiminde Uluslararası Perspektifler” olarak çevrilebilir. “OkTáv” kısaltması, Macarca başlığa atıfta bulunmaktadır. Proje lideri Dr. habil László Révész'dir (Eszterházy Károly Katolik Üniversitesi, Macaristan). Projenin süresi 27 aydır (01.10.2024'ten 31.12.2026'ya kadar). OkTáv Projesi aşağıdaki çıktıları geliştirir ve uygular: Uluslararası sorumluluk, dil öğrenimi ve öğretimi ile dijital öğrenme fırsatlarının keşfini ele alan bir literatür taraması. Macaristan genelinde uluslararası hareketlilik alanındaki iyi uygulamaların belgelenmesi (Mező, 2025a, 2025b; Molnár, 2025a, 2025b; Orgoványi-Gajdos, 2025a, 2025b), Romanya (Borbely ve ark. 2025a, 2025b, 2025c; Tódor & Pál, 2025a, 2025b), Slovak (Horváth, 2025a, 2025b) ve Sırp (Borsos, 2025a, 2025b, 2025c) okullarında uluslararası hareketlilik alanındaki iyi uygulamaların belgelenmesi. Öğrenciler ve öğretim görevlileri için tutum, görüş ve memnuniyet anketleri; katılımcıları uluslararası hareketliliğe hazırlayan üniversite derslerinde ön ve son test olarak kullanılabilir. Tutum, bir konuya ilişkin bilgi, duygu ve davranışsal niyetlerin bütünüdür ifade eden psikolojik bir terimdir. Bu anketlerin uygulanması ve yorumlanmasına yönelik metodolojik kılavuzlar. Çalışma belgesi hazırdır ve yayın süreci devam etmektedir. “Eğitimsel Kozmopolitler: Öğretmen Eğitiminde Uluslararası Perspektifler” başlıklı 30 saatlik bir üniversite dersi. Dersin ayrıntılı açıklaması, aşağıdaki paragrafta sunulan e-yayınında bulunabilir. Uluslararası hareketliliği teşvik etmek ve buna hazırlamak amacıyla müfredatı ve ilgili üniversite dersini içeren “Eğitimsel Kozmopolitler: Öğretmen Eğitiminde Uluslararası Perspektifler” başlıklı bir çevrimiçi ders kitabı. Macaristan, Romanya, Slovakya ve Sırbistan'daki ortak üniversiteler için kuruma özgü ders açıklamaları. Ders açıklamaları hazırdır ve dört ülkenin işbirliği içindeki üniversitelerinde derslerin test edilmesi devam etmektedir. Özel bir öğretmen eğitimi kursu. Bu eğitim, öğrenci kursunu veren eğitimcileri, geliştirdikleri kursu profesyonel bir şekilde sunmaya hazırlar. Müfredatı hazırdır. İlk eğitim, Sapientia Transilvanya Macar Üniversitesi'nde (Csíkszereda, Romanya, 2-4 Eylül 2025) gerçekleştirilmiştir. Proje, dört ülkeden altı Macarca konuşulan yükseköğretim kurumu tarafından ortaklaşa yürütülmektedir. Proje konsorsiyumunun ortak kurumları şunlardır: Eszterházy Károly Katolik Üniversitesi (Macaristan, not: proje bu kurum tarafından koordine edilmektedir), Partium Hıristiyan Üniversitesi (Romanya), Transilvanya Sapientia Üniversitesi (Romanya), Selye János Üniversitesi (Slovakya), Novi Sad Üniversitesi Macar Öğretmenlik Fakültesi, Subotica (Sırbistan) ve Milton Friedman Üniversitesi (Macaristan). Aşağıdaki satırlarda bu üniversiteler tanıtılmaktadır. Uluslararası öğrenci hareketliliği birçok açıdan incelenebilir ve bu konudaki çalışmalar da çeşitli kriterlere göre sınıflandırılabilir. Bu sınıflandırmalar, konuyla ilgili teorik bilginin

düzenlenmesinde yararlı olmakla kalmaz, aynı zamanda uluslararası öğrenci hareketliliğini destekleyen programların tasarlanması ve uygulanması için teorik bir çerçeve de sağlayabilir. Öğretmenlik eğitiminde öğrencilerin uluslararası hareketliliğini destekleyen bu tür üniversite programlarından biri, altı Avrupa üniversitesiyle işbirliği içinde uygulanan Oktáv programıdır. Bu programın müfredatı tamamlanmış, program kapsamında geliştirilen ilk dersler ortak üniversitelerde başlatılmış ve bunların etkisini değerlendirmek için gerekli ölçümler şu anda devam etmektedir.